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[Effect of eccentric and concentric contraction mode on myogenic regulatory factors expression in human vastus lateralis muscle](#)

Abstract:

Skeletal muscle contractions are caused to release myokines by muscle fiber. This study investigated the myogenic regulatory factors, as MHC I, IIA, IIX, Myo-D, MRF4, Murf, Atrogin-1, Decorin, Myonectin, and IL-15 mRNA expression in the response of eccentric vs concentric contraction. Eighteen healthy men were randomly divided into two eccentric and concentric groups, each of 9 persons. Isokinetic contraction protocols included maximal single-leg eccentric or concentric knee extension tasks at 60°/s with the dominant leg. Contractions consisted of a maximum of 12 sets of 10 reps, and the rest time between each set was 30 s. The baseline biopsy was performed 4 weeks before the study, and post-test biopsies were taken immediately after exercise protocols from the vastus lateralis muscle. The gene expression levels were evaluated using Real-Time PCR methods. The eccentric group showed a significantly lower RPE score than the concentric group ($P \leq 0.05$). A significant difference in MyoD, MRF4, Myonectin, and Decorin mRNA, were observed following eccentric or concentric contractions ($P \leq 0.05$). The MHC I, MHC IIA, IL-15 mRNA has been changed significantly compared to the pre-exercise in the concentric group ($P \leq 0.05$). While only MHC IIX and Atrogin-1 mRNA changed significantly in the eccentric group ($P \leq 0.05$). Additionally, the results showed a significant difference in MyoD, MRF4, IL-15, and Decorin at the follow-up values between eccentric or concentric groups ($P \leq 0.05$). Our findings highlight the growing importance of elucidating the different responses of muscle growth factors associated with a myogenic activity such as MHC IIA, Decorin, IL-15, Myonectin, Decorin, MuRF1, and MHC IIX mRNA in following various types of exercise.

Keywords: Eccentric contraction, Concentric contraction, Gene expression, Myogenic regulatory factors

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